

TRANSTERMINOLOGIZATION AND DETERMINOLOGIZATION OF INTERNATIONAL TERMS

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Abstract: The processes occurring in terminology are directly related to the development of science and technology. Thus, with the development of sciences, the emergence of new concepts and ideas is inevitable. Each discovery or scientific direction creates the need to name concepts that do not exist in this field. At this time, certain scientific concepts are expressed by giving new meanings to lexical units existing in the vocabulary of the language. The development and integration of sciences in the modern century has led to the transfer of terms from one field of science to another. At this point, the event of transterminologization takes place. Along with transterminologization, the phenomenon of determinism is also found in linguistics. While in the beginning many terms covered a limited functional area, after a certain period the scope of use of these terms expands, thus creating a process of determinologization. Nowadays, the process of determinism of terms occurs mainly as a result of the widespread dissemination of scientific and technical knowledge.

Keywords: international terms, transterminologization, determinologization, implicit, explicit.

Introduce. The emergence of new scientific ideas and research areas, the development of new technologies and the creation of technological processes lead to the emergence of new concepts and the formation of terms denoting these concepts. The reasons for the emergence of new terms in language are various, and this process manifests itself in two directions: intralinguistic and extralinguistic. The semantic change of words in the lexical system of the language, the transfer of terms from one terminological system to another terminological system is an intralinguistic process. As science, technology and integration processes develop globally, there is a necessity to name new concepts and notions. In such cases, this approach is used to name newly emerged concepts by giving new meaning to existing units in the vocabulary of language.

The essence of the process of term formation by the semantic method is that it involves not the creation of new words to express this or that new concept, but the expression of certain scientific concepts by giving new meanings to lexical units already existing in the language.

Problem statement. Each science has its own terminological system. The term is usually used in the one scientific field. For example, *oversold*, *Wi-Fi*, *ekstradisiya*, *telemarketing*. But the same term can be used in different areas. In this case, the term has special meanings.

The integration of sciences and the emergence of new social relations have led to the transfer of terms from one field of science to another. Recently, in various areas of science, there has been a process of unification of previously separate subjects. With the development of science, there is a trend toward the division of specialties into narrower subfields, along with the emergence of interdisciplinary field by reinterpreting specific terminological units, systems, and connections.

Integration of related sciences leads to the formation of synthetic scientific systems. While interdisciplinary sciences rely to some extent on the terminological resources of the sciences from which they originate, they undoubtedly develop their own highly specialized terminological systems. This allows use of the same linguistic units to express similar or different concepts. Such interactions between terminological systems naturally result in the borrowing terms from other fields. In some cases, these

terminological units do not acquire any new meaning, that the word is adopted along with its associated concept.

In relative sciences (e.g. biochemistry, biophysics, radio astronomy, geophysics, geochemistry, etc.), the entire terminological system of the foundational sciences is often utilized, as they incorporate corresponding concepts into their subsystems. For example, geophysics includes physics terms such as *maqnetizm, cazibə, plazma*.

There are frequent cases to encounter interdisciplinary interaction between systems that are not directly related to each other (e.g., the introduction of cybernetics ideas into biology, its application in medicine, mathematization of sciences, etc.). At this time, the phenomenon of term conversion occurs. M.Ismailova notes that during integration and differentiation, the phenomenon of term conversion also takes place. Term conversion refers to the complete or partial semantic modification of a term from one field while preserving its morphological and phonetic structure. As a result of this process, a new term is created. This method is called transterminologization [5, p.91].

In terminology, transterminologization refers to the process of incorporating an existing term, with either a full or partial change in its meaning, into the terminological system of another field, there by transforming it into an interfiled homonym. This is considered one of the methods of term creation and terminological conversion. During transterminologization, a terminological unit gains new semantic nuances in two forms:

1. Explicit description of new content;
2. Implicit description of new content.

Thus, units transferred to a new terminological system are subjected to either explicit or implicit transterminologization. Explicit transterminologization involves acquiring a new definition, differing from the definition in the source terminological system. Explicit transterminologization is manifested in the following ways: 1) changing the content of differential semantic features while retaining the original archiseme; 2) gaining new archisemes; 3) forming a new archiseme and replacing certain differential semantic features.

In explicit transterminologization, a term undergoes changes in the process of transition from one scientific field to another. For example, the term *agent* (agent) can have following meanings: 1) economics – broadly, it refers to a person working instead of another person, under their supervision; in a narrow sense – it donates an authorized person hired to carry out tasks such as concluding agreements [2, p.10]; 2) in logistics – a legal entity or an individual authorized to act on behalf of another person or organization; 3) in computer science – a program or utility that performs certain tasks automatically at a certain moment (or under specific conditions) [3, p.31].

As seen in the example, the common semantic feature of performing tasks is preserved across all meanings. However, in the last case, the term, which represents an object, concept, or event (the subject of action), expands its meaning by designating a program (the object of action). In other words, it becomes metaphorical.

Thus, by adding a differential semantic feature to the original meaning of the word *agent*, it has transitioned into the fields of economics, logistics and informatics, where it has been integrated into their terminological systems.

In implicit transterminologization, the term's semantic do not transform as it moves one scientific field to another; instead, it adapts based on its new context of use. For example, linguistic term *syntax* (sintaksis) is also used in the fields of informatics and mathematics. 1) In linguistics the branch of linguistics that studied the methods of forming word combinations and sentences, their syntactic forms, and the meanings they express [1, p.476]. 2) In informatics – a set of rules for creating correct (possible) sentence structures in a language. In other words, *syntax* (sintaksis) is a set of rules that determine the structure of a language and the relationships between its elements. This term applies to both natural languages and programming languages [3, p.725].

In this sense, the term has been implicitly transposed into both the humanities and the technical fields.

Spoiler (spoyler) – 1) in technical fields – a device in a car that converts turbulent air flow into laminar and reduces air resistance; 2) in aviation – turning off the lift force on the wings of an airplane [7, p.124]; 3) in informatics – someone who, by revealing information about something that must remain unknown (for example, the ending of a work of art or the outcome of a sports competition), spoils the general mood. Also refers to any anticipated yet undesirably revealed event, shared through email or new groups [3, p.703]. The same term is used in different fields, acquiring different defining meanings: technical → aviation → computer science.

Post (post) – 1) in the military, a group of guards or soldiers placed in a specific location to protect or keep something under surveillance; 2) In railway transportation – a location where production processes are managed through telemechanic, signaling, etc. 3) a responsible position. 4) in information – it is a text message on the internet that can include multimedia content like photos, videos and audio. Broadly, any type of information posted online is considered a post [3]. Apparently, the generally accepted meaning of the term “post” is “place”. 1) a scientific place for observation; 2) a controlled place; 3) a place of service related to the performance of certain work; 4) a place for sharing information online. Based on this common seme, the term has transterminologized.

Bobsleigh (bobsley) – 1. In sport – a sport that involves competing in a bobsleigh, controlled on a fast descent along an artificial ice track [6, p.62]. 2. In journalism – a filming technique using a subjective camera that maximally conveys the sense of motion [8, p.28]. The term “bobsleigh” transitioned from the sphere of sports into the sphere of journalism. The main meaning of the term, used in both fields, is associated with the meaning of fast movement.

During transterminologization, terms often expand their meanings when used across different fields. For example, the word *underwriting* (anderraytinq) in economics is understood as the process of actions on behalf of the issuer of investments in order to attract investors and place the securities issued by them on the market [2, p.21]. In insurance – the process of evaluating risks (such as the insured’s health, financial capabilities, or the condition of insured property) to decide on insurance rates and terms [9, p.8].

A *benchmark* (bençmark) is a standard used for comparison in finance. Reference securities are commonly used when evaluating other securities [2, p.42]. Thus, the meaning of the term has been expanded to mean a standard or criterion that can be used to measure the quality or outcome of something.

The development of a term within its own terminological system in a new sense should be distinguished from transterminologization. Despite the repeatedly expressed opinion regarding the singularity of term’s meaning, polysemy is observed the terminological system. For example, a *demon* is an inf. 1. Network software operating in the background. 2. A procedure that is automatically launched when certain conditions are met. 3. A service program hidden from the user, called during the performing some function [3, p.125]; *float* (flout) – 1) banknotes and coins in an organization’s reserves; 2) The period between receiving a check and paying it. 3) The number of shares of a company traded on the stock market [2, p.122]; *overnight* (overnayt) – 1) a short-term interbank loan agreement repayable the next banking day; 2) a foreign currency exchange transaction carried out on the first business day after the day the agreement was concluded; 3) financial transactions carried out within one business day [2, p.289]. The first of the meanings given to the terms we have chosen is the fundamental meaning of that concept, and other terminological meanings have emerged as derivatives of the main one.

The polysemy of terms can be explained by various reasons: 1) development in the structure of the concept expressed by the term; 2) semantic development of the current meaning of the term with the emergence of a new scientific concept; 3) acquisition of a new meanings by the term; 4) changes in scientific concepts, that necessitate new content for the term.

Since the phenomenon of transterminologization occurs in language, the process of determinologization also occurs. There is a constant between terminological and general vocabulary. During determinologization a term extends beyond its functional domain. The process of a term entering general literary language begins from the moment when the concept expressed by a special term becomes accessible to the public and widespread.

When transitioning to the general layer, a term acquires those connotations that lead to its complete determinologization. In this process of determination, a term that belongs to a terminological system loses its specific features and becomes a unit of the general language fund, gaining a broader scope of application. This process leads to the loss of scientific precision of the term, as well as the expansion of its scope of application. This phenomenon is facilitated by the rapid development of science and technology facilities, as the media actively reflects processes and research outcomes, thus enabling the transition of terms from specialized to general vocabulary.

This is what causes the transition of terms from specialized vocabulary to general vocabulary. One of the most important and significant issues when talking about the status of a term is the relationship between the term itself, which is the main specialized lexical unit, and the word, which is the main unit of language. Initially, many terms, such as *Wi-Fi*, *skaner (scanner)*, *modem*, and *printer*, had limited usage. Overtime, their usage expanded, leading to the process of determinologization.

Schematically, the stages of definition process can be outlined as follows:

The stages of the determinologization process are: narrow-scope term → specialized term → term exhibiting diversity and polysemy → term with generalized meaning → general vocabulary word.

Conclusion.

It is worth noting that modern English terms do not necessarily go through all these stage to become part of general usage. Frequently used terms in contemporary times quickly integrate into everyday language. The internationalization and popularization of many terms, along with the expansion and intensification of international relations, contribute to incorporating international terms into general vocabulary, where they become widely used by speakers.

In general, linguistic analysis shows that semantic methods play a significant role in term creation, particularly for expressing various concepts in scientific fields.

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